

THE STUDY STAGES OF THE LIFE AND STATE ACTIVITY OF AMIR TIMUR IN FRANCE IN THE 16TH CENTURY

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Abstract

This article highlights the study of Amir Temur's life and statesmanship in France in the 16th century. Factors that led to the study of Amir Temur's activities in the field of statehood by orientalists such as Jean Bodin and Louis Le Roy were included in this study.

Key words: Amir Temur, Francis I, Jean Bodin, Louis Le Roy, College de France, Franco-Ottoman alliance, religious wars, universalism.

Introduction. The rise of religious wars in the internal politics of France in the 16th century and the desire of the French kings to achieve an absolute monarchy created the need to study the statesmanship of Amir Temur among the great rulers of the Maze. Similarly, during this period, the increasing influence of the Habsburgs throughout Western Europe led to the establishment of relations between France and the Ottoman state. The main goal of the two partner states was to prevent their territories in North Africa and the Middle East from being controlled by the Habsburgs. Therefore, in 1536, the "French-Ottoman" alliance was formed between the King of France Francis I and the Sultan of the Ottoman Empire Suleiman I. The union of the representatives of the Christian and Muslim countries has been seriously criticized in France. However, the success of joint military expeditions between the two countries led to the growth of the countries' military and economic sectors. The acceleration of the exchange of ambassadors led to the transfer of the research of Eastern languages and culture in France to the patronage and control of the king. As a result, by the middle of the 16th century, the study of the Arabic language was started at the Royal College (College de France).

Literature analysis and method. Information about Amir Temur in the works of several French historians, such as "Six Books of the Republic", "Book on the vicissitude or variety of things in the universe", "History of the Great Tamerlan" which provide information about the period under study. the data were comparatively and critically analyzed and scientific conclusions were substantiated. Also, based on the principles of scientificity, objectivity, and

historicity, the method of comparative analysis was used in the research of scientific views presented in scientific literature.

Discussion and results. The collection and study of Oriental manuscripts in France reached a special stage in 1536 when French ambassadors led by Jean de la Foret were sent to Constantinople. Guillaume Postel, who worked as a translator in this diplomatic mission, was also tasked with collecting interesting manuscripts for the royal library. The French orientalist studied social life in the Ottoman Empire along with the search for sources. During the period of struggle between Catholics and Protestants in France, the concept of “universalism”^{*} appeared in the views of Guillaume Postel, who observed that Christians, Muslims and Jews lived under one rule, in harmony, in Asia Minor. Initially, in the first half of the 16th century, this idea did not achieve high results in France, but during the religious wars, the concept of universalism became one of the main tasks of scientists.

Although this idea did not achieve high results in France in the first half of the 16th century, Jean Bodin (1530-1596) made a great contribution to popularizing the concept of universalism during the religious wars. In 1576, the French jurist spoke about the issues of universalism, sovereignty, public law in the work “Six Books of the Republic” [1]. This work is considered the highest of the studies conducted by Jean Bodin and brought great fame to the country. Chapter V of the second book of the study discusses the issue of tyranny in the work of Roman emperors such as Solon, Julius Caesar and Nero, the importance of the legend of Hercules, and the relationship between Amir Temur and Sultan Bayazid [1, 253-255]. In the study, it is emphasized that it is necessary to correctly analyze the policy of Sahibqiran towards the Ottoman Turks, that it was the reason for the breaking of the military power of the Ottoman Empire by Amir Temur in order to ensure justice, and the saving of Constantinople from the invasion policy of Sultan Bayazid [1, 255]. In addition, this research focuses on the issue of religious tolerance policy of Amir Temur towards different nationalities living under his rule.

Louis Le Roy (1510-1577) was an orientalist who extensively analyzed the life and state activities of Amir Temur in France in the 16th century. If we take into account that the work “Book on the vicissitude or variety of things in the universe” [3, 118] published by the French historian in 1576, was published in the period of political and religious crises in France, then the orientalist

^{*} Explanation: Universalism is a moral worldview opposite to individualism, a way of thinking that considers the universe as a whole.

presented to the French government and people several famous things of the past. While studying the activities of the rulers comparatively, it was pointed out that the ideas that serve for the development of the country can be used as a model. For example, the author emphasized that the interpretation of the history of the 15th century should begin with the coverage of the Sahibkiran era [3, 97-a]. In the work, rulers such as Nin, Sesostris, Cyrus II, Darius I, Alexander the Great, Arshak, Hannibal, Julius Caesar, Constantine, Attila, Charlemagne, etc. investigated the activities of Amir Temur in depth, illuminating the management system. For example, the author studied the march for Egypt, which took place from the dynamics of Sahibkiran's "Seven-year" marches, geographically. After the conquest of Syrian territories by Sahibqiran, many citizens who survived the conflict fled to North Africa, but Amir Temur could not continue his march to Egypt and Sudan because of the problem of sandy deserts and water shortage. is noteworthy [3, 97-a]. The author did not dwell on the conflict between Amir Temur and the ruler of Egypt. The main task for Louis Le Roy was to study the reason why Sahibkqiran did not continue his march towards the North African regions, to analyze the socio-economic conditions. It can be assumed that the intended purpose was the development of theoretical knowledge in preparing France for the upcoming war in the Middle East region.

Similarly, another issue that Louis Le Roy aimed at covering the history of Amir Temur was to study the Sahibkqiran's attitude to the religious sphere in the second half of the 16th century. It is not an exaggeration to say that the author studied Amir Temur's participation in this field in a comparative analysis with the activities of great rulers of the past and applied it to society as a model. To this, the author says: "If Attila did not go to Rome due to his religious will and at the request of the Pope, Amir Temur did not allow the destruction of temples and did not attack Arabia because it was the birthplace of the Prophet" can be cited as an example [3, 109-a].

In the last years of the 16th century in France, special emphasis was placed on the issue of Temur studies, especially on the study of Amir Temur's life and state activities. This was primarily due to the religious conflicts that have been going on in the country for many years, and the attempt to occupy Eastern countries was one of the second reasons for the problem. Especially, the desire of the French nobles to always be in the king's attention required them to have great knowledge about the East, especially the Middle East. Because of this, representatives of the upper class began to send some people from their families to study the activities and history of the countries located in the Middle East

region, starting from the second half of the 16th century. One such person was Jean du Bec (1540-1610), who came from a powerful French archbishop's family, was bishop of several churches during the main part of his career and one of the advisors of King Henry IV. During his trip to the Middle East region, the French writer came across a work in Arabic that covered the history of Amir Timur [2, 2]. However, as Jean du Bec did not know Arabic, he turned to a local citizen who knew Italian, and the translator partially translated this work into Latin [2, 2]. The work was then re-edited by Jean du Bec and published in 1595 as a study entitled "History of the Great Tamerlan" [2]. The noteworthy aspect of this research is that it is the first time in the history of France that a work has been published under the name of Amir Temur. Because, until the 16th century, a separate work covering only the work of Sahibkiran was not written.

Conclusions. The outbreak of religious wars in France in the 16th century and the desire of the French kings for an absolute monarchy created the need to study the activities of the great rulers of the past in the country. Therefore, French orientalist focused on researching the activities of Amir Temur as an enlightened monarch.

References:

1. Bodin I. Les Six livres de la République. – Paris: Chez Jacques du Puys, Libraire Juré, à la Samaritaine, 1577. – 759 p
2. Du bec J. Histoire du grand Tamerlan. – Rouen: Richard l'Allemant, 1595 – 520 p.
3. Louis Le Roy. De la vicissitude ou variete des choses en l'univers, et concurrence des armes et des lettres par les premieres et plus illustres nations du monde, depuis le temps où àcommencé la ciuilité, & memoire humaine iusques à present. – Paris: Chez Pierre l'Huilier, rue S. Jacques à l'Oliuier, 1576 – 118 p.

